

Supplementary material for article published in Clinical Experimental Allergy:

Positive basophil histamine release assay predicts insufficient response to standard-dosed omalizumab in patients with chronic spontaneous urticaria

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Supplementary Table 1. Disease characteristics of adult patients with chronic spontaneous urticaria relative to basophil histamine release assay (BHRA) status.

	Patients with negative BHRA n=332 (86.2%)	Patients with positive BHRA n=53 (13.8%)	P-value
Disease characteristics			
Sex, female	234 (70.5)	45 (84.9)	0.029
Age, years, mean (SD)	39.9 (15.5)	44.2 (39.0)	0.072
Duration, years, mean (SD)	6.0 (9.0)	4.4 (7.7)	0.200
Smoking	143 (43.1)	16 (30.2)	0.077
Family history of urticaria	66 (19.9)	6 (11.3)	0.136
Angioedema	135 (40.7)	43 (81.1)	<0.001
CIndU*	69 (20.8)	3 (5.7)	0.016
Thyroid disease	36 (10.8)	12 (22.6)	0.007
Diabetes	10 (3.0)	4 (7.5)	0.101
Arthritis	18 (5.4)	0 (0)	0.083
Hypertension	26 (7.8)	6 (11.3)	0.393
Psychiatric disease	61 (18.4)	11 (20.8)	0.680
Asthma	56 (16.9)	8 (15.1)	0.747
Hay fever	80 (24.1)	12 (22.6)	0.818
Food allergy	36 (10.8)	5 (9.4)	0.757
Atopic dermatitis	27 (8.1)	7 (13.2)	0.227
UAS7, mean (SD)	21.2 (14.1)	25.9 (15.2)	0.031
Itch subscore, mean (SD)	11.7 (7.6)	12.7 (7.6)	0.398
Wheal subscore, mean (SD)	9.5 (7.7)	13.4 (8.3)	0.002
History of oral corticosteroid use	76 (22.9)	26 (49.1)	<0.001
Blood samples			
BHRA value (% release), median (min-max)	2.00 (0-16)	46.00 (17-84)	<0.001
Total IgE (kU/L), median (min-max)	97.00 (1-12400)	23.00 (1-1140)	<0.001
IgE <10 kU/L, n (%)	16 (5.3)	15 (30.6)	
IgE 10-50 kU/L, n (%)	80 (26.6)	18 (36.7)	
IgE 51-100 kU/L, n (%)	57 (18.9)	9 (18.4)	
IgE 101-150 kU/L, n (%)	46 (15.3)	2 (4.1)	
IgE >150 kU/L, n (%)	102 (33.9)	5.00 (10.2)	
CRP (mg/L), median (min-max)	2.00 (0.30-96.0)	4.00 (1.0-210)	0.033
Eosinophils (x 10 ⁹ /L), median (min-max)	0.15 (0-1.07)	0.10 (0-0.61)	<0.001
Basophils (x 10 ⁹ /L), median (min-max)	0.04 (0-0.20)	0.01 (0-0.06)	<0.001
Eosinophil/basophil ratio, median (min-max)	4.00 (0-31.00)	7.00 (0-61.0)	0.016
Neutrophils (x 10 ⁹ /L), median (min-max)	4.00 (1.40-11.40)	4.69 (1.40-12.0)	0.037
TSH (mIU/L), median (min-max)	1.45 (0-87.00)	1.77 (0.10-3.73)	0.032
IgG-anti-TPO (IU/mL), median (min-max)	8.00 (8.00-472)	66.0 (8.0-600)	0.005
IgG-anti-thyroglobulin (IU/mL), median (min-max)	32.0 (32.0-330)	32.0 (32.0-555)	0.529
Thyroxine (T4) (ug/dL), median (min-max)	92.0 (56.0-157)	98.0 (62.0-122)	0.739

Categorical variables are number (percentage), continuous variables are mean (standard deviation) or median (min-max). *CIndU; chronic inducible urticaria: includes cold urticaria, cholinergic urticaria, aquagenic urticaria, symptomatic dermographism, delayed pressure urticaria, solar urticaria, heat urticaria, contact urticaria, and vibratory angioedema. UAS7; urticaria activity score in the past 7 days, BHRA; basophil histamine release assay, IgE; immunoglobulin E, CRP; C-reactive protein, TSH; thyroid peroxidase, TPO; thyroid peroxidase. Data were available for: IgG-anti-thyroglobulin (n=84), IgG-anti-TPO (n=84), T4 (n=83).

Supplementary Table 2. Diagnostic properties of biomarkers for distinguishing CSU patients with BHRA-positivity and BHRA-negativity.					
Biomarker	Area under the curve (95% CI)	Sensitivity, % (95% CI)	Specificity, % (95% CI)	Positive predictive value, % (95% CI)	Negative predictive value, % (95% CI)
Total IgE	0.75 (0.68-0.83)				
IgE <10 kU/L		32.6 (21.7-42.9)	94.5 (92.9-96.5)	53.6 (35.6-70.5)	87.8 (85.9-89.7)
IgE <50 kU/L		67.4 (53.2-79.4)	64.6 (61.8-66.9)	27.0 (21.3-31.8)	91.1 (87.2-94.4)
IgE <100 kU/L		87.0 (74.1-94.5)	46.0 (43.5-47.5)	23.8 (20.3-25.9)	94.8 (89.6-97.8)
IgE <150 kU/L		89.1 (76.7-95.9)	32.5 (30.1-33.8)	20.4 (17.6-21.9)	93.9 (86.9-97.7)
Basophils	0.87 (0.81-0.92)				
Basophils <0.01 x 10 ⁹ /L		26.0 (16.9-33.3)	97.2 (95.4-98.7)	65.0 (42.2-83.2)	87.0 (85.4-88.3)
Eosinophils	0.66 (0.58-0.74)				
Eosinophils <0.05 x 10 ⁹ /L		24.5 (14.9-35.6)	91.6 (90.0-93.4)	32.5 (19.8-47.2)	88.0 (86.5-89.8)
Eosinophils <0.10 x 10 ⁹ /L		49.1 (36.2-61.9)	72.0 (69.8-74.1)	22.4 (16.5-28.3)	89.5 (86.9-92.2)
Neutrophils	0.59 (0.50-0.68)				
CRP	0.59 (0.50-0.67)				
TSH	0.59 (0.51-0.67)				
IgG-anti-TPO	0.74 (0.56-0.92)				
Overall UAS7 score	0.60 (0.51-0.69)				
Wheal subscore	0.63 (0.54-0.72)				
UAS7 score <1 point		91.8 (81.1-97.3)	12.0 (10.3-12.9)	14.6 (12.9-15.5)	90.0 (76.8-96.7)
UAS7 score <7 points		83.7 (71.2-92.0)	21.2 (19.0-22.4)	14.8 (12.6-16.3)	88.7 (80.1-94.5)
UAS7 score <16 points		75.5 (61.9-85.9)	38.8 (36.6-40.5)	16.8 (13.8-19.1)	90.6 (85.4-94.6)
UAS7 score <28 points		55.1 (41.3-68.3)	59.5 (57.3-61.7)	18.2 (13.7-22.6)	89.0 (85.6-92.2)
BHRA; basophil histamine release assay, IgE; immunoglobulin E, CRP; C-reactive protein, TSH; thyroid peroxidase, TPO; thyroid peroxidase, UAS7; urticaria activity score in the past 7 days.					